

Target fishing

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Quercetin Target fishing prediction by PLATO
Dr Mark Christopher Arokiaraj, MD DM,
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Pondicherry, India

Target	score	reliable
Aldehyde reductase:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cyclin-dependent kinase 1/cyclin B1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cell division protein kinase 5:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Adenosine A2a receptor:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Beta-lactamase AmpC:Escherichia coli K-12	13.00	yes
Enoyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] reductase:Escherichia coli K-12	13.00	yes
Cyclin-dependent kinase 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Death-associated protein kinase 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase I:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member C21:Mus musculus	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase IX:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Aldose reductase:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
C-C chemokine receptor type 4:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Malate dehydrogenase:Thermus thermophilus	13.00	yes
ELAV-like protein 3:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase SYK:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytochrome P450 1A1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Beta-chymotrypsin:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Phosphodiesterase 2A:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Proteasome Macropain subunit MB1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Replicase polyprotein 1ab:SARS coronavirus	13.00	yes
Enoyl-acyl-carrier protein reductase:Plasmodium falciparum	13.00	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase YES:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Urease subunit alpha/Urease subunit beta:Helicobacter pylori (strain ATCC 700392 / 26695) (Campylobacterpylori)	13.00	yes
Cyclooxygenase-2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Liver glycogen phosphorylase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Xanthine dehydrogenase:Bos taurus	13.00	yes
Alpha-synuclein:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Human immunodeficiency virus type 1 integrase:Human immunodeficiency virus 1	13.00	yes
Monoamine oxidase A:Bos taurus	13.00	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase SRC:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytochrome P450 3A4:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Salivary alpha-amylase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes

Cyclin-dependent kinase 6:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase VB:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Serine/threonine-protein kinase PLK1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Aldose reductase:Bos taurus	13.00	yes
Neuraminidase:Influenza A virus (A/Puerto Rico/8/1934(H1N1))	13.00	yes
Arachidonate 15-lipoxygenase:Oryctolagus cuniculus	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase II:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Arachidonate 12-lipoxygenase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Butyrylcholinesterase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
NUAK family SNF1-like kinase 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytochrome P450 1A2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Glucose-6-phosphate 1-dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Matrix metalloproteinase 13:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Acetylcholinesterase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytosol aminopeptidase:Sus scrofa	13.00	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase receptor FLT3:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Nitric oxide synthase, inducible:Mus musculus	13.00	yes
Fatty acid synthase:Plasmodium falciparum	13.00	yes
PI3-kinase p110-gamma subunit:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase IV:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Epidermal growth factor receptor erbB1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Interleukin-8 receptor A:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Serine/threonine-protein kinase Aurora-B:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Leukocyte elastase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Beta amyloid A4 protein:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
3-oxoacyl-acyl-carrier protein reductase:Plasmodium falciparum	13.00	yes
Monoamine oxidase A:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
ALK tyrosine kinase receptor:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Casein kinase II alpha:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Serine/threonine-protein kinase B-raf:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Hexokinase:Trypanosoma brucei brucei (strain 927/4 GUTat10.1)	13.00	yes
Glycogen synthase kinase-3 beta:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Vasopressin V2 receptor:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Insulin-like growth factor I receptor:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes

G-protein coupled receptor 35:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Monocarboxylate transporter 1:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Aldose reductase:Sus scrofa	13.00	yes
Matrix metalloproteinase-2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Hepatocyte growth factor receptor:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Serine/threonine-protein kinase PIM1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Prolyl endopeptidase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Estradiol 17-beta-dehydrogenase 2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase LCK:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
NADPH oxidase 4:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Hypoxia-inducible factor 1-alpha inhibitor:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Sorbitol dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Protein kinase N1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Inositol polyphosphate multikinase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase XII:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Solute carrier family 2, facilitated glucose transporter member 4:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase VII:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase XIII:Mus musculus	13.00	yes
Inositol hexakisphosphate kinase 2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytochrome P450 2C8:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytochrome P450 2C9:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Glyoxalase I:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytochrome P450 19A1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
CaM kinase II beta:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
M18 aspartyl aminopeptidase:Plasmodium falciparum 3D7	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase VI:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Matrix metalloproteinase 9:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
D-alanine-D-alanine ligase:Helicobacter pylori (strain HPAG1)	13.00	yes
Neuraminidase:Influenza A virus	13.00	yes
Lysine-specific histone demethylase 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Myeloperoxidase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Maltase-glucoamylase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Protein-tyrosine phosphatase 1B:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
ATP-binding cassette sub-family G member 2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Sarcoplasmic/endoplasmic reticulum calcium ATP-ase:Oryctolagus cuniculus	13.00	yes

Xanthine dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytochrome P450 2C19:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Adenosine A3 receptor:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Lactoperoxidase:Bos taurus	13.00	yes
Matrix metalloproteinase 12:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Dipeptidyl peptidase IV:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Focal adhesion kinase 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Matrix metalloproteinase 3:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cyclin-dependent kinase 5/CDK5 activator 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Calmodulin:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
ELAV-like protein 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Glutathione reductase:Saccharomyces cerevisiae S288c	13.00	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase receptor RET:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Trypsin I:Bos taurus	13.00	yes
Lymphocyte differentiation antigen CD38:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Arachidonate 15-lipoxygenase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Phospholipase A2 group 1B:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Serine/threonine-protein kinase AKT:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Urokinase-type plasminogen activator:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cyclin-dependent kinase 4/cyclin D1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Chymotrypsin C:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Serine/threonine-protein kinase NEK6:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Beta-secretase 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Tyrosinase:Agaricus bisporus	13.00	yes
Sialidase:Clostridium perfringens	13.00	yes
Multidrug resistance-associated protein 4:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
D-alanylalanine synthetase:Escherichia coli K-12	13.00	yes
PI3-kinase p85-alpha subunit:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Monoamine oxidase B:Bos taurus	13.00	yes
5'-nucleotidase:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase III:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Epoxide hydratase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Monocarboxylate transporter 2:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Aldehyde reductase:Sus scrofa	13.00	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase receptor UFO:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase XIV:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Multidrug resistance-associated protein 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cyclin-dependent kinase 2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes

Short transient receptor potential channel 5:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Serine/threonine-protein kinase NEK2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Adenosine A1 receptor:Rattus norvegicus	13.00	yes
Cyclin-dependent kinase 1/cyclin B:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Beta-lactamase:Enterobacter cloacae	13.00	yes
Dopamine D4 receptor:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Solute carrier family 2, facilitated glucose transporter member 2:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Aldose reductase:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Arginase:Leishmania amazonensis	13.00	yes
Thrombin:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
P-glycoprotein 1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Carbonic anhydrase VA:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Monoamine oxidase B:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytochrome P450 1B1:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Cytochrome P450 2D6:Homo sapiens	13.00	yes
Genome polyprotein:Zika virus	12.53	yes
Tyrosinase:Homo sapiens	12.41	yes
Synapsin-1:Bos taurus	12.35	yes
Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase SETD7:Homo sapiens	12.34	yes
Arginase-1:Rattus norvegicus	12.33	yes
Cruzipain:Trypanosoma cruzi	12.33	yes
Protein E6:Human papillomavirus type 16	12.31	yes
Alkaline phosphatase, tissue-nonspecific isozyme:Homo sapiens	12.24	yes
Intestinal alkaline phosphatase:Mus musculus	12.24	yes
Thiosulfate sulfurtransferase:Homo sapiens	12.24	yes
HSP60/HSP10:Homo sapiens	12.24	yes
GroEL/GroES:Escherichia coli	12.24	yes
Dihydroorotate dehydrogenase (fumarate):Leishmania major	12.18	yes
Microtubule-associated protein tau:Homo sapiens	12.18	yes
Fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase:Homo sapiens	12.13	yes
Alkaline phosphatase placental-like:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
Insulin-degrading enzyme:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
Myosin light chain kinase, smooth muscle:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
DNA dC- γ dU-editing enzyme APOBEC-3G:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
Insulin receptor:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
Heat shock protein HSP 90-beta:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes

Probable DNA dC- ζ dU-editing enzyme APOBEC-3A:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
Lysine-specific demethylase 4D-like:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
Replicase polyprotein 1ab:Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2	12.12	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase transforming protein FPS:Fujinami sarcoma virus	12.12	yes
DNA topoisomerase II alpha:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
DNA-(apurinic or apyrimidinic site) lyase:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
Cystathionine beta-synthase:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
RNase L:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
Canalicular multispecific organic anion transporter 1:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2:Homo sapiens	12.12	yes
DNA repair protein RAD52 homolog:Homo sapiens	12.06	yes
Receptor-type tyrosine-protein phosphatase S:Homo sapiens	11.97	yes
Induced myeloid leukemia cell differentiation protein Mcl-1:Homo sapiens	11.96	yes
Estradiol 17-beta-dehydrogenase 1:Homo sapiens	11.90	yes
Cytoplasmic zinc-finger protein:Caenorhabditis elegans	11.87	yes
MAP kinase signal-integrating kinase 2:Homo sapiens	11.86	yes
Zinc finger protein mex-5:Caenorhabditis elegans	11.85	yes
Solute carrier family 22 member 12:Rattus norvegicus	11.84	yes
Sortase A:Streptococcus mutans	11.84	yes
Islet amyloid polypeptide:Homo sapiens	11.84	yes
Solute carrier family 22 member 12:Homo sapiens	11.84	yes
Low molecular weight phosphotyrosine protein phosphatase:Bos taurus	11.84	yes
Sortase A:Staphylococcus aureus	11.84	yes
Estrogen receptor beta:Homo sapiens	11.84	yes
DNA-3-methyladenine glycosylase:Homo sapiens	11.84	yes
Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma:Mus musculus	11.83	yes
M1-family aminopeptidase:Plasmodium falciparum 3D7	11.80	yes
Fatty acid synthase:Homo sapiens	11.78	yes
Dopamine transporter:Rattus norvegicus	11.78	yes
MAP kinase-interacting serine/threonine-protein kinase MNK1:Homo sapiens	11.77	yes
Protein polybromo-1:Homo sapiens	11.74	yes
Casein kinase II alpha'/beta:Homo sapiens	11.74	yes

Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member B10:Homo sapiens	11.74	yes
DNA topoisomerase 1:Rattus norvegicus	11.74	yes
Tankyrase-1:Homo sapiens	11.74	yes
Transthyretin:Homo sapiens	11.74	yes
Poly [ADP-ribose] polymerase-1:Homo sapiens	11.74	yes
GATA4/NKX2-5:Mus musculus	11.74	yes
Tankyrase-2:Homo sapiens	11.74	yes
Seed lipoxygenase-1:Glycine max	11.74	yes
Intestinal alkaline phosphatase:Homo sapiens	11.56	yes
Pancreatic alpha-amylase:Sus scrofa	11.36	yes
P-glycoprotein 3:Mus musculus	11.32	yes
Glucose transporter:Homo sapiens	11.26	yes
Acidic alpha-glucosidase:Rattus norvegicus	11.26	yes
CDGSH iron-sulfur domain-containing protein 1:Homo sapiens	11.26	yes
Estrogen-related receptor alpha:Homo sapiens	11.26	yes
Carboxy-terminal domain RNA polymerase II polypeptide A small phosphatase 1:Homo sapiens	11.26	yes
Beta-glucuronidase:Homo sapiens	11.26	yes
Aryl hydrocarbon receptor:Homo sapiens	11.26	yes
Neuraminidase:Influenza A virus (strain A/USSR/90/1977 H1N1)	11.26	yes
Androgen Receptor:Homo sapiens	11.26	yes
Beta-galactoside alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 1:Homo sapiens	11.24	yes
CMP-N-acetylneuraminic acid-beta-galactosaminidase alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase:Rattus norvegicus	11.24	yes
Telomerase reverse transcriptase:Homo sapiens	11.20	yes
LXR-beta:Homo sapiens	11.12	yes
LXR-alpha:Homo sapiens	11.12	yes
Adenosine A2a receptor:Homo sapiens	10.95	yes
Cyclooxygenase-1:Homo sapiens	10.91	yes
Mitochondrial import inner membrane translocase subunit TIM23:Saccharomyces cerevisiae S288c	10.86	yes
Mitochondrial import inner membrane translocase subunit TIM10:Saccharomyces cerevisiae S288c	10.86	yes
Voltage-gated L-type calcium channel alpha-1C subunit:Rattus norvegicus	10.80	yes
Plasminogen:Homo sapiens	10.74	yes
Lysozyme C:Rattus norvegicus	10.64	yes
Beta-glucuronidase:Rattus norvegicus	10.64	yes

Probable low molecular weight protein-tyrosine-phosphatase:Myobacterium tuberculosis	10.62	yes
Protein-tyrosine phosphatase G1:Homo sapiens	10.62	yes
Hematopoietic cell protein-tyrosine phosphatase 70Z-PEP:Homo sapiens	10.62	yes
Phosphotyrosine protein phosphatase:Myobacterium tuberculosis	10.62	yes
Phosphatidylinositol 3,4,5-trisphosphate 5-phosphatase 2:Homo sapiens	10.49	yes
6-phosphofructo-2-kinase/fructose-2,6-bisphosphatase 3:Homo sapiens	10.49	yes
G protein-coupled receptor kinase 6:Homo sapiens	10.39	yes
UDP-glucuronosyltransferase 1-1:Homo sapiens	10.39	yes
Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase EZH1:Homo sapiens	10.39	yes
Pyruvate kinase isozymes M1/M2:Homo sapiens	10.39	yes
Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase SMYD3:Homo sapiens	10.39	yes
Sialidase 2:Homo sapiens	10.39	yes
Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase MLL:Homo sapiens	10.39	yes
Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase NSD2:Homo sapiens	10.39	yes
Estrogen receptor alpha:Homo sapiens	10.29	yes
Glucocorticoid receptor:Homo sapiens	10.15	yes
Sucrase-isomaltase:Rattus norvegicus	10.06	yes
Arachidonate 12-lipoxygenase:Rattus norvegicus	10.06	yes
Progesterone receptor:Homo sapiens	10.06	yes
Sucrase-isomaltase:Homo sapiens	10.06	yes
Arachidonate 15-lipoxygenase, type II:Rattus norvegicus	10.06	yes
Protein kinase Pfmrk:Plasmodium falciparum	9.89	yes
Delta opioid receptor:Homo sapiens	9.85	yes
Mucin-1:Homo sapiens	9.76	yes
NACHT, LRR and PYD domains-containing protein 3:Homo sapiens	9.76	yes
Myocilin:Homo sapiens	9.76	yes
Alpha-glucosidase:Blautia obeum	9.68	yes
Stem cell growth factor receptor:Homo sapiens	9.68	yes
Glutaminy-peptide cyclotransferase:Homo sapiens	9.62	yes
Serine/threonine-protein kinase Aurora-A:Homo sapiens	9.54	yes
Streptokinase A:Streptococcus pyogenes serotype M1	9.52	yes
Human immunodeficiency virus type 1 reverse transcriptase:Human immunodeficiency virus 1	9.48	yes
Dipeptidyl peptidase IV:Sus scrofa	9.44	yes

Taste receptor type 2 member 31:Homo sapiens	9.42	yes
Dihydroorotate dehydrogenase:Plasmodium falciparum	9.36	yes
Dihydroorotate dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens	9.36	yes
CMP-N-acetylneuraminate-beta-1,4-galactoside alpha-2,3-sialyltransferase:Rattus norvegicus	9.36	yes
Tubulin alpha chain:Sus scrofa	9.21	yes
Nuclear receptor subfamily 0 group B member 1:Homo sapiens	9.20	yes
Apoptosis regulator Bcl-X:Homo sapiens	9.20	yes
Phospholipase A2 group IIA:Homo sapiens	9.11	yes
HERG:Homo sapiens	9.04	yes
Alpha-L-fucosidase 1:Bos taurus	8.94	yes
Delta opioid receptor:Mus musculus	8.92	yes
Mu opioid receptor:Mus musculus	8.92	yes
Cyclooxygenase-1:Ovis aries	8.90	yes
Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase-6-phosphogluconolactonase:Plasmodium berghei	8.86	yes
Inhibitor of nuclear factor kappa B kinase beta subunit:Homo sapiens	8.83	yes
Neurotrophic tyrosine kinase receptor type 2:Homo sapiens	8.83	yes
Cyclooxygenase-2:Mus musculus	8.79	yes
mRNA interferase MazF:Escherichia coli K-12	8.75	yes
Apoptosis regulator Bcl-2:Homo sapiens	8.73	yes
Serotonin 2c (5-HT2c) receptor:Homo sapiens	8.69	yes
Carbonyl reductase [NADPH] 1:Homo sapiens	8.68	yes
Angiotensin-converting enzyme:Homo sapiens	8.56	yes
Phospholipase C-gamma-1:Homo sapiens	8.48	yes
Cyclin-dependent kinase 9:Homo sapiens	8.34	yes
Acetylcholinesterase:Electrophorus electricus	8.30	yes
Regulator of G-protein signaling 17:Homo sapiens	8.27	yes
Voltage-gated potassium channel subunit Kv1.5:Homo sapiens	8.24	yes
Ornithine decarboxylase:Homo sapiens	8.22	yes
Cell division protein kinase 8:Homo sapiens	8.18	yes
CDK9/cyclin T1:Homo sapiens	8.17	yes
CDK7/Cyclin H/MNAT1:Homo sapiens	8.17	yes
CDK2/Cyclin A:Homo sapiens	8.17	yes
Voltage-gated potassium channel, IKs; KCNQ1(Kv7.1)/KCNE1(MinK):Homo sapiens	8.16	yes
Voltage-gated potassium channel subunit Kv4.3:Homo sapiens	8.16	yes

Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma:Homo sapiens	8.13	yes
Matrix metalloproteinase-1:Homo sapiens	8.13	yes
Vascular endothelial growth factor A:Homo sapiens	8.07	yes
Placenta growth factor:Homo sapiens	8.07	yes
Tyrosinase:Mus musculus	7.99	yes
Adenosine A1 receptor:Homo sapiens	7.98	yes
Serotonin 1d (5-HT1d) receptor:Sus scrofa	7.94	yes
1-phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-1:Bos taurus	7.94	yes
Delta opioid receptor:Sus scrofa	7.94	yes
Poly [ADP-ribose] polymerase 2:Homo sapiens	7.94	yes
Dopamine D3 receptor:Homo sapiens	7.94	yes
Transitional endoplasmic reticulum ATPase:Homo sapiens	7.94	yes
GABA-A receptor; alpha-1/beta-2/gamma-2:Homo sapiens	7.94	yes
dTDP-4-dehydrorhamnose reductase:Mycobacterium tuberculosis	7.89	yes
Macrophage migration inhibitory factor:Homo sapiens	7.78	yes
Lysine-specific demethylase 5A:Homo sapiens	7.71	yes
Phosphodiesterase 5A:Homo sapiens	7.69	yes
NEDD8-activating enzyme E1 regulatory subunit:Homo sapiens	7.60	yes
Prostaglandin E synthase:Homo sapiens	7.57	yes
Mannose-6-phosphate isomerase:Homo sapiens	7.57	yes
Thromboxane-A synthase:Homo sapiens	7.26	yes
Androgen Receptor:Rattus norvegicus	7.18	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase FYN:Homo sapiens	7.16	yes
Polyadenylate-binding protein 1:Homo sapiens	7.05	yes
Pancreatic triacylglycerol lipase:Sus scrofa	6.96	yes
NAD-dependent deacetylase sirtuin 1:Homo sapiens	6.75	yes
Signal transducer and activator of transcription 3:Homo sapiens	6.73	yes
Solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 1B1:Homo sapiens	6.71	yes
Solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 1B3:Homo sapiens	6.71	yes
Heat shock factor protein 1:Mus musculus	6.65	yes
Testis-specific androgen-binding protein:Homo sapiens	6.62	yes
Solute carrier family 2, facilitated glucose transporter member 4:Mus musculus	6.60	yes

Monoamine oxidase A:Rattus norvegicus	6.57	yes
Cyclooxygenase-1:Bos taurus	6.55	yes
Phosphodiesterase 4D:Homo sapiens	6.54	yes
DNA (cytosine-5)-methyltransferase 1:Homo sapiens	6.54	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase BMX:Homo sapiens	6.52	yes
Tyrosine-protein kinase ABL:Homo sapiens	6.52	yes
Dual specificity mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase 4:Homo sapiens	6.52	yes
Serotonin 2a (5-HT2a) receptor:Homo sapiens	6.52	yes
Alpha-mannosidase:Canavalia ensiformis	6.52	yes
Cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator:Rattus norvegicus	6.52	yes
Dopamine transporter:Homo sapiens	6.52	yes
Estrogen-related receptor beta:Homo sapiens	6.52	yes
Voltage-dependent L-type calcium channel subunit alpha-1C:Cavia porcellus	6.52	yes
Aldehyde oxidase:Homo sapiens	6.52	yes
7,8-dihydro-8-oxoguanine triphosphatase:Homo sapiens	6.43	yes
Aldehyde dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens	6.35	yes
Caspase-3:Homo sapiens	6.34	yes
Sentrin-specific protease 8:Homo sapiens	6.34	yes
Sentrin-specific protease 6:Homo sapiens	6.34	yes
Sentrin-specific protease 7:Homo sapiens	6.34	yes
Human immunodeficiency virus type 2 integrase:Human immunodeficiency virus 2	6.31	yes
Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(I)/G(S)/G(T) subunit beta-1/gamma-2:Homo sapiens	6.08	yes
Beta-lactamase:Pseudomonas aeruginosa	6.08	yes
Beta-lactamase:Salmonella choleraesuis (strain SC-B67)	6.08	yes
Beta Lactamase:Pseudomonas aeruginosa	6.08	yes
Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase liver:Homo sapiens	6.04	yes
Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 10:Homo sapiens	6.02	yes
Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 2:Homo sapiens	6.02	yes
Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 6:Homo sapiens	6.02	yes
Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 1:Homo sapiens	6.02	yes

Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 3:Homo sapiens	6.02	yes
Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 14:Homo sapiens	6.02	yes
Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 13:Homo sapiens	6.02	yes

tid: 12051
chembl id: [CHEMBL3871](#)
name: Aldehyde reductase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:2.32µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10980
chembl id: [CHEMBL279](#)
name: Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:682nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 104296
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1907602](#)
 name: Cyclin-dependent kinase 1/cyclin B1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:20.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:6.53µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 101596
chembl id: [CHEMBL5901](#)
name: Cell division protein kinase 5:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 EC50:63.4µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11736
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL302](#)
 name: Adenosine A2a receptor:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 Ki:6.99μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 Ki:7.58μM</p>	1.00												

tid: 10027
chembl id: [CHEMBL2026](#)
name: Beta-lactamase AmpC:Escherichia coli K-12

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:4.00µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 110
chembl id: [CHEMBL1857](#)
name: Enoyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] reductase:Escherichia coli K-12

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:20.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12071
chembl id: [CHEMBL308](#)
name: Cyclin-dependent kinase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:450nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11150
chembl id: [CHEMBL2558](#)
name: Death-associated protein kinase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:8.90µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:31.0µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 10193
chembl id: [CHEMBL261](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase I:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:2.68μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 102817
chembl id: [CHEMBL1075270](#)
name: Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member C21:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:6.90µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12952
chembl id: [CHEMBL3594](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase IX:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:7.00µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12543
chembl id: [CHEMBL2622](#)
name: Aldose reductase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:5.17μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL6492 IC50:2.29μM</p>	1.00												

tid: 10579
chembl id: [CHEMBL2414](#)
name: C-C chemokine receptor type 4:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:21.7µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 100248

chembl id: [CHEMBL4255](#)

name: Malate dehydrogenase:Thermus thermophilus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:6.00µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 117529
chembl id: [CHEMBL4105924](#)
name: ELAV-like protein 3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:1.80µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10906
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2599](#)
 name: Tyrosine-protein kinase SYK:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:20.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
 CHEMBL28 IC50:4.20µM	1.00												

tid: 11113
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2231](#)
 name: Cytochrome P450 1A1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:3.43µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:427nM</p>	1.00												

tid: 10909
chembl id: [CHEMBL4796](#)
name: Beta-chymotrypsin:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:100.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10595
chembl id: [CHEMBL4650](#)
name: Phosphodiesterase 2A:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:81.3µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 100624

chembl id: [CHEMBL4662](#)

name: Proteasome Macropain subunit MB1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:2.65µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
 CHEMBL28 IC50:1.34µM	1.00												

tid: 101075
chembl id: [CHEMBL5118](#)
name: Replicase polyprotein 1ab:SARS coronavirus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:13.9µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 100456
chembl id: [CHEMBL4150](#)
name: Enoyl-acyl-carrier protein reductase:Plasmodium falciparum

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:1.78μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:50.0μM</p>	1.00												

tid: 18033
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2073](#)
 name: Tyrosine-protein kinase YES:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 Ki:472nM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:3.30µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 117195
 chembl id: [CHEMBL3885651](#)
 name: Urease subunit alpha/Urease subunit beta:Helicobacter pylori (strain ATCC 700392 / 26695) (Campylobacter-pylori)

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:11.1µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 126
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL230](#)
 name: Cyclooxygenase-2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:28.6µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:8.00µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 11442
chembl id: [CHEMBL2568](#)
name: Liver glycogen phosphorylase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:4.80µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12161
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3649](#)
 name: Xanthine dehydrogenase:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:31.9µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:6.04µM</p>	1.00												
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:15.4µM</p>								1.00		1.00			

tid: 102780
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL6152](#)
 name: Alpha-synuclein:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:20.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:8.20µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 12456
chembl id: [CHEMBL3471](#)
name: Human immunodeficiency virus type 1 integrase:Human immunodeficiency virus 1

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:6.27µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:1.50µM</p>	1.00												
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:2.41µM</p>								1.00		1.00			

tid: 10709
chembl id: [CHEMBL3254](#)
name: Monoamine oxidase A:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:10.0nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10434
chembl id: [CHEMBL267](#)
name: Tyrosine-protein kinase SRC:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:1.34µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 17045
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL340](#)
 name: Cytochrome P450 3A4:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:2.11µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:9.20µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 12166
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL312](#)
 name: Arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:575nM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:10.00µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 10706
chembl id: [CHEMBL2478](#)
name: Salivary alpha-amylase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:21.4µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10480
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2508](#)
 name: Cyclin-dependent kinase 6:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:25.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:1.70µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 11016
chembl id: [CHEMBL3969](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase VB:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:11.9µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10907
chembl id: [CHEMBL3024](#)
name: Serine/threonine-protein kinase PLK1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:19.2µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 17058
chembl id: [CHEMBL3081](#)
name: Aldose reductase:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:10.2μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 21
chembl id: [CHEMBL2051](#)
name: Neuraminidase:Influenza A virus (A/Puerto Rico/8/1934(H1N1))

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:7.75µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 20075
chembl id: [CHEMBL4358](#)
name: Arachidonate 15-lipoxygenase:Oryctolagus cuniculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:3.99µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 15
chembl id: [CHEMBL205](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase II:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:2.54μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11134
chembl id: [CHEMBL3687](#)
name: Arachidonate 12-lipoxygenase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:440nM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:860nM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 10532
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1914](#)
 name: Butyrylcholinesterase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 Ki:68.0μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 Ki:37.4μM</p>	1.00												

tid: 101332
chembl id: [CHEMBL5784](#)
name: NUAK family SNF1-like kinase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:5.09µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12594
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3356](#)
 name: Cytochrome P450 1A2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:2.52µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
 CHEMBL28 IC50:795nM	1.00												

tid: 101159
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL5347](#)
 name: Glucose-6-phosphate 1-dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL1520590 IC50:31.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11024
chembl id: [CHEMBL280](#)
name: Matrix metalloproteinase 13:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:8.46µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 93
chembl id: [CHEMBL220](#)
name: Acetylcholinesterase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 Ki:38.3μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00							1.00
<p>CHEMBL164 IC50:12.0nM</p>							1.00	1.00		1.00			
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:12.0nM</p>	1.00												
<p>CHEMBL31574 IC50:12.0nM</p>							1.00			1.00		1.00	

tid: 101481
chembl id: [CHEMBL5624](#)
name: Cytosol aminopeptidase:Sus scrofa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:34.3µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12670

chembl id: [CHEMBL1974](#)

name: Tyrosine-protein kinase receptor FLT3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:590nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
 CHEMBL28 IC50:1.45µM	1.00												

tid: 11039
chembl id: [CHEMBL3464](#)
name: Nitric oxide synthase, inducible:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:16.4μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 100454
chembl id: [CHEMBL4512](#)
name: Fatty acid synthase:Plasmodium falciparum

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:1.50µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11939
chembl id: [CHEMBL3267](#)
name: PI3-kinase p110-gamma subunit:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:13.8µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12896
chembl id: [CHEMBL3729](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase IV:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:7.89µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 9

chembl id: [CHEMBL203](#)

name: Epidermal growth factor receptor erbB1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:3.66µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11574
chembl id: [CHEMBL4029](#)
name: Interleukin-8 receptor A:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:4.75µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10781

chembl id: [CHEMBL2185](#)

name: Serine/threonine-protein kinase Aurora-B:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:910nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11540
chembl id: [CHEMBL4051](#)
name: Cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 Kd:25.6μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 Ki:81.0μM</p>	1.00												

tid: 235
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL248](#)
 name: Leukocyte elastase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:14.3µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:46.1µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 10656
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2487](#)
 name: Beta amyloid A4 protein:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:11.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:23.0µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 100455
chembl id: [CHEMBL4513](#)
name: 3-oxoacyl-acyl-carrier protein reductase:Plasmodium falciparum

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:5.40µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 86
chembl id: [CHEMBL1951](#)
name: Monoamine oxidase A:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:2.61μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:1.32μM</p>	1.00												

tid: 100417
chembl id: [CHEMBL4247](#)
name: ALK tyrosine kinase receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:3.32μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10044
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3629](#)
 name: Casein kinase II alpha:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 Ki:1.18μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:800nM</p>	1.00												

tid: 100126
chembl id: [CHEMBL5145](#)
name: Serine/threonine-protein kinase B-raf:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:7.59µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 103997
chembl id: [CHEMBL1741201](#)
name: Hexokinase:Trypanosoma brucei brucei (strain 927/4 GUTat10.1)

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:22.4µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10197
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL262](#)
 name: Glycogen synthase kinase-3 beta:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:2.00µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:1.90µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 112
chembl id: [CHEMBL1790](#)
name: Vasopressin V2 receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:15.9µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 234

chembl id: [CHEMBL1957](#)

name: Insulin-like growth factor I receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:300nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 103700
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1293267](#)
 name: G-protein coupled receptor 35:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:15.4μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:28.2μM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 104650
chembl id: [CHEMBL2073709](#)
name: Monocarboxylate transporter 1:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:14.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11251
chembl id: [CHEMBL4559](#)
name: Aldose reductase:Sus scrofa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:50.1µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 13001
chembl id: [CHEMBL333](#)
name: Matrix metalloproteinase-2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:6.68µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11451

chembl id: [CHEMBL3717](#)

name: Hepatocyte growth factor receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:580nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10839

chembl id: [CHEMBL2147](#)

name: Serine/threonine-protein kinase PIM1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:402nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11968
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3202](#)
 name: Prolyl endopeptidase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:13.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:36.0µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 13053

chembl id: [CHEMBL2789](#)

name: Estradiol 17-beta-dehydrogenase 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:1.54µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10140
chembl id: [CHEMBL258](#)
name: Tyrosine-protein kinase LCK:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:13.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 103508
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1250375](#)
 name: NADPH oxidase 4:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:680nM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:1.13µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 101604
chembl id: [CHEMBL5909](#)
name: Hypoxia-inducible factor 1-alpha inhibitor:Homo sapi-ens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:10.2µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11447
chembl id: [CHEMBL2275](#)
name: Sorbitol dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:35.6µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11637
chembl id: [CHEMBL3384](#)
name: Protein kinase N1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:5.80µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 119151

chembl id: [CHEMBL4523401](#)

name: Inositol polyphosphate multikinase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:2.30µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
 CHEMBL28 IC50:29.0µM	1.00												

tid: 12209
chembl id: [CHEMBL3242](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase XII:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:9.39μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 108368
chembl id: [CHEMBL3286066](#)
name: Solute carrier family 2, facilitated glucose transporter member 4:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:16.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11060
chembl id: [CHEMBL2326](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase VII:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:4.84μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10989
chembl id: [CHEMBL2186](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase XIII:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:9.03μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 119238

chembl id: [CHEMBL4523488](#)

name: Inositol hexakisphosphate kinase 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:700nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
 CHEMBL28 IC50:7.10µM	1.00												

tid: 10163
chembl id: [CHEMBL3721](#)
name: Cytochrome P450 2C8:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:2.70µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12911
chembl id: [CHEMBL3397](#)
name: Cytochrome P450 2C9:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:10.2µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10278
chembl id: [CHEMBL2424](#)
name: Glyoxalase I:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:3.20µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:11.0µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 65
chembl id: [CHEMBL1978](#)
name: Cytochrome P450 19A1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:12.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:1.81µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 10396
chembl id: [CHEMBL4121](#)
name: CaM kinase II beta:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:3.00µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 103696
chembl id: [CHEMBL1293263](#)
name: M18 aspartyl aminopeptidase:Plasmodium falciparum 3D7

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL1173475 IC50:385nM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00		1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL583912 IC50:1.38µM</p>										1.00			

tid: 10186
chembl id: [CHEMBL3025](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase VI:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:6.17μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12592
chembl id: [CHEMBL321](#)
name: Matrix metalloproteinase 9:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:529nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 106632
chembl id: [CHEMBL2366488](#)
name: D-alanine-D-alanine ligase:Helicobacter pylori (strain HPAG1)

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:48.5µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 102438
chembl id: [CHEMBL6135](#)
name: Neuraminidase:Influenza A virus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:29.5µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:33.2µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 102439
chembl id: [CHEMBL6136](#)
name: Lysine-specific histone demethylase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:1.26µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:12.5µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 10567
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2439](#)
 name: Myeloperoxidase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:1.55µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:3.80µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 1
chembl id: [CHEMBL2074](#)
name: Maltase-glucoamylase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:10.8µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 13061
chembl id: [CHEMBL335](#)
name: Protein-tyrosine phosphatase 1B:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:23.3µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 100974
chembl id: [CHEMBL5393](#)
name: ATP-binding cassette sub-family G member 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:7.24μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:4.28μM</p>	1.00												

tid: 55
chembl id: [CHEMBL215](#)
name: Arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:3.69µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 100660
chembl id: [CHEMBL4693](#)
name: Sarcoplasmic/endoplasmic reticulum calcium ATP-ase:Oryctolagus cuniculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:9.00µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 149
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1929](#)
 name: Xanthine dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:3.02µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:1.50µM</p>	1.00												
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:2.79µM</p>								1.00		1.00			

tid: 12912
chembl id: [CHEMBL3622](#)
name: Cytochrome P450 2C19:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:10.5µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 280

chembl id: [CHEMBL256](#)

name: Adenosine A3 receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:30.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 105560
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2295561](#)
 name: Lactoperoxidase:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:6.10µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:17.8µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 11871
chembl id: [CHEMBL4393](#)
name: Matrix metalloproteinase 12:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:10.2µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11140
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL284](#)
 name: Dipeptidyl peptidase IV:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:9.78µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
 CHEMBL28 IC50:140nM	1.00												

tid: 11242
chembl id: [CHEMBL2695](#)
name: Focal adhesion kinase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:1.20µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11109
chembl id: [CHEMBL283](#)
name: Matrix metalloproteinase 3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:5.57µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 104294
chembl id: [CHEMBL1907600](#)
name: Cyclin-dependent kinase 5/CDK5 activator 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:23.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:1.60µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 101444
chembl id: [CHEMBL6093](#)
name: Calmodulin:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:13.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 103512
chembl id: [CHEMBL1250379](#)
name: ELAV-like protein 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:1.40µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 19632

chembl id: [CHEMBL4119](#)

name: Glutathione reductase:*Saccharomyces cerevisiae* S288c

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:48.8µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 100079
chembl id: [CHEMBL2041](#)
name: Tyrosine-protein kinase receptor RET:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:78.1µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10443
chembl id: [CHEMBL3769](#)
name: Trypsin I:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:7.10µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 100622

chembl id: [CHEMBL4660](#)

name: Lymphocyte differentiation antigen CD38:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:37.9µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12054
chembl id: [CHEMBL2903](#)
name: Arachidonate 15-lipoxygenase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:2.20µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:9.10µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 12651
chembl id: [CHEMBL4426](#)
name: Phospholipase A2 group 1B:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:2.00µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12666
chembl id: [CHEMBL4282](#)
name: Serine/threonine-protein kinase AKT:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:5.39µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11942

chembl id: [CHEMBL3286](#)

name: Urokinase-type plasminogen activator:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:12.1µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 104295
chembl id: [CHEMBL1907601](#)
name: Cyclin-dependent kinase 4/cyclin D1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:61.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11685
chembl id: [CHEMBL2386](#)
name: Chymotrypsin C:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:100.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 30038

chembl id: [CHEMBL4309](#)

name: Serine/threonine-protein kinase NEK6:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:4.23µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12252
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4822](#)
 name: Beta-secretase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:6.79µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:38.5µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 100675
chembl id: [CHEMBL3318](#)
name: Tyrosinase:Agaricus bisporus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:31.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 101107
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL5189](#)
 name: Sialidase:Clostridium perfringens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:6.48μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:17.4μM</p>	1.00												

tid: 104069
chembl id: [CHEMBL1743128](#)
name: Multidrug resistance-associated protein 4:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:20.8µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 45
chembl id: [CHEMBL1956](#)
name: D-alanylalanine synthetase:Escherichia coli K-12

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:19.9µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10427
chembl id: [CHEMBL2506](#)
name: PI3-kinase p85-alpha subunit:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:3.80µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12232
chembl id: [CHEMBL2756](#)
name: Monoamine oxidase B:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:20.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 102910
chembl id: [CHEMBL1075214](#)
name: 5'-nucleotidase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:45.3nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 10139
chembl id: [CHEMBL2885](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase III:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:8.10µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11727
chembl id: [CHEMBL2409](#)
name: Epoxide hydratase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:33.5µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 104659
chembl id: [CHEMBL2073718](#)
name: Monocarboxylate transporter 2:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:5.00µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11600
chembl id: [CHEMBL4049](#)
name: Aldehyde reductase:Sus scrofa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:38.4µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 100410

chembl id: [CHEMBL4895](#)

name: Tyrosine-protein kinase receptor UFO:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:960nM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11063
chembl id: [CHEMBL3510](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase XIV:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:5.41µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12030

chembl id: [CHEMBL3004](#)

name: Multidrug resistance-associated protein 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:4.41μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00					1.00
 CHEMBL164 IC50:20.0μM	1.00						1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	

tid: 11678
chembl id: [CHEMBL301](#)
name: Cyclin-dependent kinase 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:40.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 103525
chembl id: [CHEMBL1250411](#)
name: Short transient receptor potential channel 5:Homo sapi-ens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:6.50µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 30017

chembl id: [CHEMBL3835](#)

name: Serine/threonine-protein kinase NEK2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:5.73µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 12512
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL318](#)
 name: Adenosine A1 receptor:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 Ki:2.47μM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 Ki:3.00μM</p>	1.00												

tid: 104709
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2094127](#)
 name: Cyclin-dependent kinase 1/cyclin B:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:75.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:4.00µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 12802
chembl id: [CHEMBL2725](#)
name: Beta-lactamase:Enterobacter cloacae

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:85.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 90
chembl id: [CHEMBL219](#)
name: Dopamine D4 receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:7.85µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 102691
chembl id: [CHEMBL5873](#)
name: Solute carrier family 2, facilitated glucose transporter member 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:12.0µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 242
chembl id: [CHEMBL1900](#)
name: Aldose reductase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:900nM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:11.9µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 107995
chembl id: [CHEMBL3108635](#)
name: Arginase:Leishmania amazonensis

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:4.00µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11
chembl id: [CHEMBL204](#)
name: Thrombin:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:6.71µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 11398
chembl id: [CHEMBL4302](#)
name: P-glycoprotein 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:52.5µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:41.0µM</p>	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 11042
chembl id: [CHEMBL4789](#)
name: Carbonic anhydrase VA:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 Ki:6.81μM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 104
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2039](#)
 name: Monoamine oxidase B:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:59.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:3.79µM</p>	1.00												

tid: 10147
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4878](#)
 name: Cytochrome P450 1B1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL50 IC50:492nM</p>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:94.9nM</p>	1.00												

tid: 11365

chembl id: [CHEMBL289](#)

name: Cytochrome P450 2D6:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL50 IC50:18.8µM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

tid: 119671
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4523954](#)
 name: Genome polyprotein:Zika virus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:53.0µM</p>		1.00			0.86				1.00		1.00		1.00
<p>CHEMBL164 IC50:5.35µM</p>	0.94	0.99	0.96		0.78	1.00	0.99		1.00		1.00		

tid: 73
chembl id: [CHEMBL1973](#)
name: Tyrosinase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:60.0µM</p>					0.86				1.00		1.00		1.00
<p>CHEMBL150 IC50:1.00µM</p>	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94		0.76	0.93			1.00		0.98	
<p>CHEMBL446323 IC50:5.12µM</p>								0.99					

tid: 116805
chembl id: [CHEMBL3817719](#)
name: Synapsin-1:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL413552 IC50:150nM	0.94	1.00	0.96	0.95	0.83	0.92	0.99	0.98	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.98	0.79

tid: 100877
chembl id: [CHEMBL5523](#)
name: Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase SETD7:Homo sapi-ens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 IC50:6.08μM					0.86			0.97	1.00		1.00		1.00
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:6.02μM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98		0.87	0.89			1.00		0.98	

tid: 108287
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3232699](#)
 name: Arginase-1:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL31574 IC50:1.40µM	0.89	1.00	0.92	0.92	0.87	0.77	0.96	1.00		1.00		1.00	
 CHEMBL151 IC50:9.00µM									1.00		1.00		1.00

tid: 10452
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3563](#)
 name: Cruzipain:Trypanosoma cruzi

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL31574 IC50:30.0µM</p>	0.89	1.00	0.92	0.92	0.87	0.77	0.96	1.00		1.00		1.00	
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:27.3µM</p>									1.00		1.00		1.00

tid: 104501
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2010633](#)
 name: Protein E6:Human papillomavirus type 16

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:850nM	0.94	0.99	0.84	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:4.00µM	1.00	0.98	0.87	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.69

tid: 101624
chembl id: [CHEMBL5979](#)
name: Alkaline phosphatase, tissue-nonspecific isozyme:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL70501 IC50:19.5µM</p>					0.86								0.71
<p>CHEMBL164 IC50:33.2µM</p>	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96		0.78	1.00		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	
<p>CHEMBL234338 EC50:43.4µM</p>								0.99					

tid: 12754

chembl id: [CHEMBL3151](#)

name: Intestinal alkaline phosphatase:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL70501 IC50:7.57µM					0.86								0.71
 CHEMBL164 IC50:12.5µM	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96		0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	

tid: 118080
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4295835](#)
 name: Thiosulfate sulfurtransferase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL253570 IC50:330nM			0.93		0.84		0.97	0.98	1.00		1.00		0.79
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:57.0µM	0.89	1.00		0.98		0.87				1.00		0.98	

tid: 117701
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4106131](#)
 name: HSP60/HSP10:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL253570 IC50:7.50µM			0.93		0.84		0.97	0.98	1.00		1.00		0.79
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:11.0µM	0.89	1.00		0.98		0.87				1.00		0.98	

tid: 117709
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4106139](#)
 name: GroEL/GroES:Escherichia coli

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL253570 IC50:905nM			0.93		0.84		0.97	0.98	1.00		1.00		0.79
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:6.65µM	0.89	1.00		0.98		0.87				1.00		0.98	

tid: 118088
chembl id: [CHEMBL4295843](#)
name: Dihydroorotate dehydrogenase (fumarate):Leishmania major

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL164 IC50:30.8µM</p>	0.94	1.00	0.99		0.84		1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62
<p>CHEMBL226034 IC50:96.8µM</p>				0.99		0.81							

tid: 103657
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1293224](#)
 name: Microtubule-associated protein tau:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL164 IC50:1.20µM</p>	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	
<p>CHEMBL3663941 IC50:13.4µM</p>													0.67

tid: 11415
chembl id: [CHEMBL3975](#)
name: Fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL253570 IC50:24.0µM</p>			0.93		0.84	0.81	0.97			0.98		0.97	0.79
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:29.0µM</p>		1.00						1.00		1.00			
<p>CHEMBL611029 IC50:8.70µM</p>		0.89		0.97			0.99						

tid: 11919
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3402](#)
 name: Alkaline phosphatase placental-like:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL164 EC50:32.3μM</p>	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62
<p>CHEMBL234338 EC50:59.6μM</p>							0.99						

tid: 103720
chembl id: [CHEMBL1293287](#)
name: Insulin-degrading enzyme:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:100.0µM	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 10250

chembl id: [CHEMBL2428](#)

name: Myosin light chain kinase, smooth muscle:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 Ki:1.70µM	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 104013
chembl id: [CHEMBL1741217](#)
name: DNA dC- γ dU-editing enzyme APOBEC-3G:Homo sapi-ens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:2.39 μ M	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 35
chembl id: [CHEMBL1981](#)
name: Insulin receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 Ki:2.60μM	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 11748
chembl id: [CHEMBL4303](#)
name: Heat shock protein HSP 90-beta:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:13.5µM	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 103975
chembl id: [CHEMBL1741179](#)
name: Probable DNA dC-¿dU-editing enzyme APOBEC-3A:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL164 IC50:17.5µM</p>	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 103659
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1293226](#)
 name: Lysine-specific demethylase 4D-like:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:3.00µM	0.94	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62	
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:3.00µM	1.00							1.00		1.00			

tid: 119301
chembl id: [CHEMBL4523582](#)
name: Replicase polyprotein 1ab:Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL164 IC50:297nM</p>	0.94		0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99		1.00		1.00	0.62
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:3.02µM</p>	1.00												
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:20.0nM</p>								1.00		1.00			

tid: 101513
chembl id: [CHEMBL5708](#)
name: Tyrosine-protein kinase transforming protein
FPS:Fujinami sarcoma virus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL164 Ki:1.80μM</p>	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 63
chembl id: [CHEMBL1806](#)
name: DNA topoisomerase II alpha:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:390nM	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 101476
chembl id: [CHEMBL5619](#)
name: DNA-(apurinic or apyrimidinic site) lyase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:320nM	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 109567
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3399911](#)
 name: Cystathionine beta-synthase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:18.8µM	0.94	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62
 CHEMBL65320 IC50:17.1µM	1.00												

tid: 11353
chembl id: [CHEMBL3575](#)
name: RNase L:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:264μM	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 101311
chembl id: [CHEMBL5748](#)
name: Canalicular multispecific organic anion transporter
1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL164 IC50:22.0µM</p>	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 11848
chembl id: [CHEMBL3736](#)
name: Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL164 IC50:10.00µM	0.94	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	0.78	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.62

tid: 105690
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2362978](#)
 name: DNA repair protein RAD52 homolog:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL253570 IC50:2.34µM	0.84	1.00	0.93	0.94	0.84	0.81	0.97	0.98	1.00		1.00	0.97	0.79
 CHEMBL583912 IC50:1.45µM										1.00			

tid: 107614
chembl id: [CHEMBL2396508](#)
name: Receptor-type tyrosine-protein phosphatase S:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL247484 IC50:17.5µM					0.80								
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:4.30µM	0.89		0.89	0.98		0.87	0.89			1.00		0.98	0.69
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:10.3µM			1.00						1.00		1.00		
 CHEMBL398328 IC50:3.00µM								0.97					

tid: 100468
chembl id: [CHEMBL4361](#)
name: Induced myeloid leukemia cell differentiation protein
Mcl-1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:2.99µM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98	0.78	0.87	0.89			1.00		0.98	0.69
 CHEMBL234338 IC50:18.8µM								0.99	1.00		1.00		

tid: 11512

chembl id: [CHEMBL3181](#)

name: Estradiol 17-beta-dehydrogenase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL150 IC50:1.05µM	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00			0.98	
 CHEMBL28 IC50:710nM	1.00												
 CHEMBL6665 IC50:1.09µM											0.94		0.64

tid: 103737

chembl id: [CHEMBL1293304](#)

name: Cytoplasmic zinc-finger protein:Caenorhabditis elegans

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 EC50:60.4µM	0.75	1.00	0.85		0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00		1.00	0.88	1.00
 CHEMBL172350 EC50:93.1µM				0.96									
 CHEMBL1423496 EC50:15.8µM										0.96			

tid: 30037

chembl id: [CHEMBL4204](#)

name: MAP kinase signal-integrating kinase 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 IC50:579nM					0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00		1.00		1.00
 CHEMBL28 IC50:308nM					0.75	1.00							
 CHEMBL293776 IC50:252nM					0.93								
 CHEMBL77588 IC50:1.70µM					0.88					0.92		0.90	

tid: 103752

chembl id: [CHEMBL1293319](#)

name: Zinc finger protein mex-5:Caenorhabditis elegans

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 EC50:31.0µM	0.75	1.00	0.85		0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00		1.00	0.88	1.00
 CHEMBL172350 EC50:36.0µM				0.96									
 CHEMBL1339669 EC50:28.8µM										0.93			

tid: 102942

chembl id: [CHEMBL1075239](#)

name: Solute carrier family 22 member 12:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:18.0µM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98	0.78	0.87	0.89	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.69

tid: 119656
chembl id: [CHEMBL4523939](#)
name: Sortase A:Streptococcus mutans

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:27.2µM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98	0.78	0.87	0.89	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.69

tid: 104362
chembl id: [CHEMBL1914266](#)
name: Islet amyloid polypeptide:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:7.80µM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98	0.78	0.87	0.89	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.69

tid: 102767

chembl id: [CHEMBL6120](#)

name: Solute carrier family 22 member 12:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:2.00µM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98	0.78	0.87	0.89	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.69

tid: 102567
chembl id: [CHEMBL1075054](#)
name: Low molecular weight phosphotyrosine protein phosphatase:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:10.00µM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98	0.78	0.87	0.89	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.69

tid: 100929
chembl id: [CHEMBL5362](#)
name: Sortase A:Staphylococcus aureus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:29.8µM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98	0.78	0.87	0.89	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.69

tid: 174

chembl id: [CHEMBL242](#)

name: Estrogen receptor beta:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:2.93µM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98	0.78	0.87	0.89	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.69

tid: 109564
chembl id: [CHEMBL3396943](#)
name: DNA-3-methyladenine glycosylase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28626 IC50:2.60µM	0.89	1.00	0.89	0.98	0.78	0.87	0.89	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.69

tid: 10961
chembl id: [CHEMBL2459](#)
name: Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma:Musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 EC50:2.30µM</p>			0.85		0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00		1.00	0.88	1.00
<p>CHEMBL28 EC50:24.9µM</p>		1.00											
<p>CHEMBL293776 EC50:7.30µM</p>			0.93										
<p>CHEMBL3314497 EC50:4.30µM</p>									0.90				
<p>CHEMBL55415 EC50:16.4µM</p>		0.80											

tid: 103745
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1293312](#)
 name: M1-family aminopeptidase:Plasmodium falciparum 3D7

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:22.9µM</p>	0.75	1.00	0.85		0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00		1.00	0.88	1.00
<p>CHEMBL172350 IC50:15.6µM</p>				0.96						0.89			

tid: 11535
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4158](#)
 name: Fatty acid synthase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:62.5µM</p>	1.00	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00			1.00	0.88	1.00
<p>CHEMBL323197 IC50:5.54µM</p>										0.89			
<p>CHEMBL361025 IC50:41.0µM</p>	0.79												

tid: 13077
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL338](#)
 name: Dopamine transporter:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 EC50:1.45µM	0.75	1.00	0.85		0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00		1.00	0.88	1.00
 CHEMBL1278226 EC50:3.42µM				0.92									
 CHEMBL1278227 EC50:12.9µM										0.91			

tid: 100835
chembl id: [CHEMBL4718](#)
name: MAP kinase-interacting serine/threonine-protein kinase
MNK1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:179nM</p>	0.75	1.00	0.85		0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00		1.00	0.88	1.00
<p>CHEMBL293776 IC50:1.20µM</p>				0.93						0.89			

tid: 104264
chembl id: [CHEMBL1795184](#)
name: Protein polybromo-1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 Kd:12.9μM	0.75	1.00	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.88	1.00

tid: 117041
chembl id: [CHEMBL3883328](#)
name: Casein kinase II alpha'/ beta:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 IC50:1.00µM	0.75	1.00	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.88	1.00

tid: 102631

chembl id: [CHEMBL5983](#)

name: Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member B10:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 IC50:9.20µM													
 CHEMBL28 IC50:15.6µM													

0.85 0.90 0.86 0.76 0.88 0.97 1.00 0.89 1.00 0.88 1.00

0.75 1.00

tid: 103103
chembl id: [CHEMBL1075164](#)
name: DNA topoisomerase 1:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 IC50:1.82µM	0.75	1.00	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.88	1.00

tid: 101462
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL6164](#)
 name: Tankyrase-1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:2.40µM</p>	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.88	1.00		
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:3.13µM</p>	0.75	1.00											

tid: 12704
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3194](#)
 name: Transthyretin:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:6.69µM</p>	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.88	1.00		
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:3.43µM</p>	0.75	1.00											

tid: 11663
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3105](#)
 name: Poly [ADP-ribose] polymerase-1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:4.23µM</p>	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.88	1.00		
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:100.0µM</p>	0.75	1.00											

tid: 117707
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4106137](#)
 name: GATA4/NKX2-5:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:22.0µM</p>	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.88	1.00		
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:24.0µM</p>	0.75	1.00											

tid: 102783
chembl id: [CHEMBL6154](#)
name: Tankyrase-2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL151 IC50:1.09µM</p>	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.88	1.00		
<p>CHEMBL28 IC50:2.93µM</p>	0.75	1.00											

tid: 100171
chembl id: [CHEMBL4586](#)
name: Seed lipoxygenase-1:Glycine max

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL151 IC50:3.20µM	0.75	1.00	0.85	0.90	0.86	0.76	0.88	0.97	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.88	1.00

tid: 101024

chembl id: [CHEMBL5573](#)

name: Intestinal alkaline phosphatase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL70501 IC50:1.11µM	0.67				0.86	0.78							0.71
 CHEMBL234338 EC50:81.0µM	1.00	0.79	0.95				0.87	0.99	1.00		1.00	0.95	
 CHEMBL1505816 IC50:24.8µM										1.00			

tid: 101520
chembl id: [CHEMBL5730](#)
name: Pancreatic alpha-amylase:Sus scrofa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL312163 IC50:73.9µM	0.74	0.78	0.96	0.99	0.72	0.88	0.93	0.98	0.87	0.96	0.94	0.95	0.67

tid: 12502
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2573](#)
 name: P-glycoprotein 3:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL150 Kd:6.70μM	1.00	1.00	0.94		0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97			0.94	0.98	
 CHEMBL165607 Kd:4.00μM				0.96									
 CHEMBL66 Kd:37.4μM									1.00	1.00			
 CHEMBL309490 Kd:5.90μM													0.54

tid: 11173
chembl id: [CHEMBL2535](#)
name: Glucose transporter:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL150 IC50:4.00µM	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.50

tid: 19672

chembl id: [CHEMBL3513](#)

name: Acidic alpha-glucosidase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL150 IC50:59.5µM	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.50

tid: 104248
chembl id: [CHEMBL1795168](#)
name: CDGSH iron-sulfur domain-containing protein 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL150 IC50:3.10µM</p>	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.50

tid: 10133
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3429](#)
 name: Estrogen-related receptor alpha:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL150 IC50:9.64μM	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00		0.98	0.50
 CHEMBL44 IC50:10.0nM											0.94		

tid: 104180
chembl id: [CHEMBL1795098](#)
name: Carboxy-terminal domain RNA polymerase II polypeptide A small phosphatase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL150 IC50:9.93μM</p>	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.50

tid: 17050
chembl id: [CHEMBL2728](#)
name: Beta-glucuronidase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL150 IC50:36.5µM	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.50

tid: 10694
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3201](#)
 name: Aryl hydrocarbon receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL150 IC50:28.0nM	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	
 CHEMBL312186 EC50:1.34µM													0.53

tid: 109720
chembl id: [CHEMBL3559643](#)
name: Neuraminidase:Influenza A virus (strain A/USSR/90/1977 H1N1)

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL150 IC50:60.0µM</p>	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.50

tid: 56
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1871](#)
 name: Androgen Receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL150 IC50:9.70µM	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.84	0.76	0.93	0.97	0.96	1.00	1.00	0.98		
 CHEMBL28 IC50:5.20µM	1.00										0.94	0.50	

tid: 109837
chembl id: [CHEMBL3596075](#)
name: Beta-galactoside alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL122701 IC50:7.50µM	0.80	1.00	0.88	0.87	0.70	0.69	0.90	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.88	0.89	0.69

tid: 12371
chembl id: [CHEMBL4276](#)
name: CMP-N-acetylneuraminate-beta-galactosamide-alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL122701 IC50:1.90µM	0.80	1.00	0.88	0.87	0.70	0.69	0.90	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.88	0.89	0.69

tid: 12622
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2916](#)
 name: Telomerase reverse transcriptase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL222541 IC50:320nM</p>					0.73		0.87	1.00					0.77
<p>CHEMBL75267 IC50:36.0µM</p>		1.00							0.96		0.88		
<p>CHEMBL4081286 IC50:969nM</p>					0.92								
<p>CHEMBL3423384 IC50:35.7µM</p>					0.78								
<p>CHEMBL4070673 IC50:1.73µM</p>							0.69						

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
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1.00

0.95

CHEMBL225227

IC50:11.0μM

0.65

CHEMBL222354

IC50:600nM

tid: 252
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL251](#)
 name: Adenosine A2a receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL3939546 Ki:25.5µM					0.72								
 CHEMBL309490 Ki:21.5µM	0.95	1.00	0.92	0.91		0.70	0.90	0.97	0.96	1.00		0.98	
 CHEMBL44 IC50:17.4µM											0.94		
 CHEMBL7334 Ki:3.50µM													0.57

tid: 96
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL221](#)
 name: Cyclooxygenase-1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL199397 IC50:30.1µM					0.70								
 CHEMBL463145 IC50:14.0µM	1.00	0.79	0.89		0.67	0.83							0.69
 CHEMBL311498 IC50:54.2µM										1.00			
 CHEMBL44 IC50:80.0µM	0.71										0.94	0.81	
 CHEMBL1684148 IC50:26.0µM								0.92					
 CHEMBL463453 IC50:67.1µM										0.96			

tid: 103976
chembl id: [CHEMBL1741180](#)
name: Mitochondrial import inner membrane translocase subunit TIM23:*Saccharomyces cerevisiae* S288c

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL309490 IC50:8.56µM</p>	0.95	1.00	0.92	0.91	0.63	0.70	0.90	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.54

tid: 103990
chembl id: [CHEMBL1741194](#)
name: Mitochondrial import inner membrane translocase subunit TIM10:*Saccharomyces cerevisiae* S288c

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL309490 IC50:35.5µM</p>	0.95	1.00	0.92	0.91	0.63	0.70	0.90	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.98	0.54

tid: 10514
chembl id: [CHEMBL3762](#)
name: Voltage-gated L-type calcium channel alpha-1C sub-unit:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL242383 IC50:27.5µM	0.84		0.86		0.75	0.64	0.88	0.97		1.00		0.98	
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:85.1µM		1.00		0.89					1.00		1.00		
 CHEMBL242385 IC50:45.1µM													0.50

tid: 12
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1801](#)
 name: Plasminogen:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL183745 IC50:2.30µM					0.63				0.87				
 CHEMBL164861 IC50:1.50µM	0.67	0.78	0.90	0.98		0.71	0.86	0.97		0.88	0.94	0.89	0.67

tid: 12136
chembl id: [CHEMBL2297](#)
name: Lysozyme C:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28 IC50:17.7µM	0.75	1.00	0.78	0.85	0.71	0.61	0.82	0.90					
 CHEMBL6665 IC50:9.70µM										0.93	0.86	0.94	0.84 0.64

tid: 10676
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4814](#)
 name: Beta-glucuronidase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28 IC50:2.80µM	0.75	1.00	0.78	0.85	0.71	0.61	0.82	0.90					
 CHEMBL6665 IC50:5.90µM									0.93	0.86	0.94	0.84	0.64

tid: 100602
chembl id: [CHEMBL4542](#)
name: Probable low molecular weight protein-tyrosine-phosphatase:Mycobacterium tuberculosis

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL463145 IC50:12.0µM	0.67	1.00	0.79	0.89	0.68	0.67	0.83	0.90	0.93		0.94	0.77	0.69
 CHEMBL1808155 IC50:2.43µM										0.86			

tid: 10756
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3236](#)
 name: Protein-tyrosine phosphatase G1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL463145 IC50:20.9µM	0.67	1.00	0.79	0.89	0.68	0.67	0.83	0.90	0.93		0.94	0.77	0.69
 CHEMBL1808155 IC50:8.52µM										0.86			

tid: 12388
chembl id: [CHEMBL2889](#)
name: Hematopoietic cell protein-tyrosine phosphatase 70Z-PEP:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL463145 IC50:30.3µM	0.67	1.00	0.79	0.89	0.68	0.67	0.83	0.90	0.93		0.94	0.77	0.69
 CHEMBL1808155 IC50:7.29µM										0.86			

tid: 117766
chembl id: [CHEMBL4295521](#)
name: Phosphotyrosine protein phosphatase:Myco bacterium tuberculosis

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL463145 IC50:1.20µM	0.67	1.00	0.79	0.89	0.68	0.67	0.83	0.90	0.93		0.94	0.77	0.69
 CHEMBL1808155 IC50:1.44µM										0.86			

tid: 105660
chembl id: [CHEMBL2331064](#)
name: Phosphatidylinositol 3,4,5-trisphosphate 5-phosphatase
2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL234338 IC50:6.00µM	0.67	1.00	0.79	0.95	0.69	0.60	0.87	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.95	0.41

tid: 105649
chembl id: [CHEMBL2331053](#)
name: 6-phosphofructo-2-kinase/fructose-2,6-bisphosphatase
3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL234338 IC50:2.97µM	0.67	1.00	0.79	0.95	0.69	0.60	0.87	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.95	0.41

tid: 102447

chembl id: [CHEMBL6144](#)

name: G protein-coupled receptor kinase 6:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL55415 IC50:6.61µM	0.80	0.79	0.92	0.71	0.64	0.83							
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:8.70µM	1.00							0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.47

tid: 103619
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1287617](#)
 name: UDP-glucuronosyltransferase 1-1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL55415 Ki:41.3µM	0.80	0.79	0.92	0.71	0.64	0.83							
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:5.55µM	1.00						0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.47	

tid: 105446

chembl id: [CHEMBL2189116](#)

name: Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase EZH1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL55415 IC50:8.77µM	0.80	1.00	0.79	0.92	0.71	0.64	0.83	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.44

tid: 103134
chembl id: [CHEMBL1075189](#)
name: Pyruvate kinase isozymes M1/M2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL55415 IC50:35.4μM	0.80	1.00	0.79	0.92	0.71	0.64	0.83	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.44

tid: 105632
chembl id: [CHEMBL2321643](#)
name: Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase SMYD3:Homo sapi-
ens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL55415 IC50:18.2µM	0.80	1.00	0.79	0.92	0.71	0.64	0.83	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.44

tid: 10678
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3200](#)
 name: Sialidase 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL55415 IC50:55.0µM	0.80	1.00	0.79	0.92	0.71	0.64	0.83	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	
 CHEMBL242385 IC50:70.0µM													0.50

tid: 103732

chembl id: [CHEMBL1293299](#)

name: Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase MLL:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL55415 IC50:2.92µM	0.80	1.00	0.79	0.92	0.71	0.64	0.83	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.44

tid: 108005
chembl id: [CHEMBL3108645](#)
name: Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase NSD2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL55415 IC50:2.65µM	0.80	1.00	0.79	0.92	0.71	0.64	0.83	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.44

tid: 19
chembl id: [CHEMBL206](#)
name: Estrogen receptor alpha:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL311640 IC50:68.0nM					0.73								0.57
 CHEMBL28 IC50:1.25µM	0.75	1.00	0.78				0.82				0.94		
 CHEMBL1082421 EC50:231nM					0.89								
 CHEMBL311878 IC50:2.95µM							0.72						0.84
 CHEMBL1087683 IC50:310nM											0.96		
 CHEMBL1082423 EC50:35.8µM								0.94					

structure

mfp1

featmfp1

rdkit7

pattern

ap_bits

tt_bits

fp2

pubchem

cdk_maccs

graph

substructure

hybridization

klekota_roth

0.93

CHEMBL44

IC50:560nM

tid: 25
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2034](#)
 name: Glucocorticoid receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:19.0µM	0.71	1.00	0.76	0.89	0.60	0.58	0.80	0.96	1.00		1.00	0.86	0.47
 CHEMBL524715 EC50:75.0µM										0.98			

tid: 12200

chembl id: [CHEMBL3114](#)

name: Sucrase-isomaltase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:52.0µM	0.71	1.00	0.76	0.89	0.60	0.58	0.80	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.47

tid: 12052

chembl id: [CHEMBL2741](#)

name: Arachidonate 12-lipoxygenase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:15.0nM	0.71	1.00	0.76	0.89	0.60	0.58	0.80	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.47

tid: 36
chembl id: [CHEMBL208](#)
name: Progesterone receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:15.0µM	0.71	1.00	0.76	0.89	0.60	0.58	0.80	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.47

tid: 11997
chembl id: [CHEMBL2748](#)
name: Sucrase-isomaltase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL8260 IC50:42.7µM	0.71	1.00	0.76	0.89	0.60	0.58	0.80	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.47

tid: 12426
chembl id: [CHEMBL3289](#)
name: Arachidonate 15-lipoxygenase, type II:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL8260 IC50:260nM</p>	0.71	1.00	0.76	0.89	0.60	0.58	0.80	0.96	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.47

tid: 20128
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4090](#)
 name: Protein kinase Pfmrk:Plasmodium falciparum

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28 IC50:7.00µM	0.75	1.00	0.78	0.85	0.71	0.61	0.82	0.90			0.94		0.50
 CHEMBL44 IC50:93.0µM									0.93	0.80		0.81	

tid: 136
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL236](#)
 name: Delta opioid receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL78010 Ki:8.40µM					0.94	0.45	0.77	0.95		0.89			
 CHEMBL63354 Ki:36.2nM		0.65	1.00			0.62		0.87		0.94	0.86	0.60	
 CHEMBL226508 Ki:3.10µM					0.77								

tid: 109790
chembl id: [CHEMBL3580494](#)
name: Mucin-1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28 IC50:76.0µM	0.75	1.00	0.78	0.85	0.71	0.61	0.82	0.90	0.86	0.77	0.94	0.77	0.50

tid: 104004
chembl id: [CHEMBL1741208](#)
name: NACHT, LRR and PYD domains-containing protein
3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28 IC50:10.00µM	0.75	1.00	0.78	0.85	0.71	0.61	0.82	0.90	0.86		0.94	0.77	0.50
 CHEMBL16312 IC50:12.9µM										0.77			

tid: 117572
chembl id: [CHEMBL4105967](#)
name: Myocilin:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL28 Kd:41.6μM	0.75	1.00	0.78	0.85	0.71	0.61	0.82	0.90	0.86	0.77	0.94	0.77	0.50

tid: 117769
chembl id: [CHEMBL4295524](#)
name: Alpha-glucosidase:Blautia obeum

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL476314 IC50:60.0µM	0.60	0.78	0.80	0.96	0.59	0.67	0.81	0.95	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.84	0.52

tid: 238

chembl id: [CHEMBL1936](#)

name: Stem cell growth factor receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL66 IC50:18.5µM					0.63				1.00	1.00			
 CHEMBL78010 IC50:949nM	0.58	0.78	0.76	0.94		0.49	0.77				0.88		
 CHEMBL1564355 IC50:1.97µM								0.97				0.89	
 CHEMBL3358999 IC50:200nM													0.33

tid: 100450
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4508](#)
 name: Glutaminyl-peptide cyclotransferase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL294878 IC50:45.2µM		1.00			0.62		0.78						
 CHEMBL3780401 IC50:27.9µM				0.93				0.95	0.84	0.83		0.84	
 CHEMBL3780265 IC50:14.2µM			0.77										
 CHEMBL3780601 IC50:37.2µM						0.55							
 CHEMBL59589 IC50:34.6µM											0.88		

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL3781227 IC50:16.1µM</p>		0.62											
<p>CHEMBL3780826 IC50:15.3µM</p>													0.50

tid: 20014
chembl id: [CHEMBL4722](#)
name: Serine/threonine-protein kinase Aurora-A:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1762119 IC50:6.20µM					0.70								
 CHEMBL487402 Ki:1.00µM	0.58	0.78	0.78	0.94			0.78	0.95			0.88	0.81	0.39
 CHEMBL6246 IC50:2.48µM						0.54			0.84				
 CHEMBL4087337 IC50:1.05µM										0.96			

tid: 103661
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1293228](#)
 name: Streptokinase A:Streptococcus pyogenes serotype M1

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1563898 EC50:10.2µM					0.54								
 CHEMBL63354 EC50:2.30µM	0.65	1.00	0.66			0.62	0.69		0.87		0.94	0.86	0.60
 CHEMBL1606646 EC50:2.56µM					0.86								
 CHEMBL459022 EC50:5.89µM										0.96			
 CHEMBL478791 EC50:1.80µM								0.95					

tid: 228
chembl id: [CHEMBL247](#)
name: Human immunodeficiency virus type 1 reverse transcriptase:Human immunodeficiency virus 1

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL390489 IC50:1.20µM</p>					0.50								
<p>CHEMBL63677 IC50:65.0µM</p>	0.73	1.00					0.76				0.94		0.60
<p>CHEMBL198873 IC50:6.90µM</p>					0.79								
<p>CHEMBL291426 IC50:62.0µM</p>			0.74					0.92		0.96		0.89	
<p>CHEMBL3593481 IC50:8.00µM</p>						0.59							

structure

mfp1

featmfp1

rdkit7

pattern

ap_bits

tt_bits

fp2

pubchem

cdk_maccs

graph

substructure

hybridization

klekota_roth

[CHEMBL36327](#)

IC50:760nM

0.88

tid: 11107
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3813](#)
 name: Dipeptidyl peptidase IV:Sus scrofa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL293776 IC50:490nM	0.64	0.78	0.76		0.57	0.54	0.77	0.95	0.87	0.89	0.88	0.85	0.30
 CHEMBL348436 IC50:430nM				0.94									

tid: 104544

chembl id: [CHEMBL2034804](#)

name: Taste receptor type 2 member 31:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL487601 IC50:11.3µM	0.58	0.78	0.79	0.95	0.52	0.59	0.80	0.95	0.84	0.89	0.88	0.85	0.43

tid: 100588

chembl id: [CHEMBL3486](#)

name: Dihydroorotate dehydrogenase:Plasmodium falciparum

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL222556 IC50:9.48µM	0.59	1.00	0.71	0.78	0.62	0.50	0.79	0.94	0.96	0.89	0.88	0.79	0.69

tid: 157

chembl id: [CHEMBL1966](#)

name: Dihydroorotate dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL222556 IC50:12.4µM	0.59	1.00	0.71	0.78	0.62	0.50	0.79	0.94	0.96	0.89	0.88	0.79	0.69

tid: 12856
chembl id: [CHEMBL3211](#)
name: CMP-N-acetylneuraminase-beta-1,4-galactoside alpha-2,3-sialyltransferase:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL222556 IC50:1.40µM	0.59	1.00	0.71	0.78	0.62	0.50	0.79	0.94	0.96	0.89	0.88	0.79	0.69

tid: 17039
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3658](#)
 name: Tubulin alpha chain:Sus scrofa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL77552 IC50:3.00µM	0.71	0.86	0.92	0.46	0.61	0.86		0.82	0.92	0.88	0.90	0.41	
 CHEMBL277148 IC50:7.30µM	0.79												
 CHEMBL123092 IC50:25.0µM							0.96						

tid: 104176
chembl id: [CHEMBL1795094](#)
name: Nuclear receptor subfamily 0 group B member 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL77552 IC50:35.0µM	0.71	0.78	0.86	0.92	0.46	0.61	0.86	0.95	0.82	0.92	0.88	0.90	0.41

tid: 100217
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4625](#)
 name: Apoptosis regulator Bcl-X:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL3828618 Ki:8.40μM</p>		0.82	0.71	0.86	0.60		0.70	0.93	0.93	0.89	0.94		0.38
<p>CHEMBL66953 IC50:2.20μM</p>		0.60				0.52							
<p>CHEMBL469424 IC50:54.2μM</p>												0.68	

tid: 10584
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3474](#)
 name: Phospholipase A2 group IIA:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL63354 IC50:23.8µM	0.65	1.00			0.41	0.62					0.94		
 CHEMBL187504 IC50:3.50µM			0.79				0.75	0.93	0.87	0.96		0.93	0.67
 CHEMBL380864 IC50:15.5µM					0.73								

tid: 165
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL240](#)
 name: HERG:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL243664 IC50:32.4µM	0.60	0.78	0.77	0.86	0.52	0.55	0.78	0.88			0.88	0.77	0.33
 CHEMBL16312 IC50:21.9µM										0.77			
 CHEMBL311663 IC50:6.03µM									0.88				

tid: 100591
chembl id: [CHEMBL3545](#)
name: Alpha-L-fucosidase 1:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:54.0µM	0.71	0.87			0.60				0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL457303 IC50:89.0µM			0.77	0.81		0.60	0.75	0.97		1.00			

tid: 10315
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3222](#)
 name: Delta opioid receptor:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL312790 Ki:12.5µM					0.42	0.61					0.94		0.44
 CHEMBL312750 Ki:12.0µM		0.58	0.78	0.79	0.94		0.78		0.82			0.85	
 CHEMBL73930 Ki:7.00µM										0.88			
 CHEMBL476121 Ki:3.60µM							0.96						

tid: 12471
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2858](#)
 name: Mu opioid receptor:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL312790 Ki:18.5µM					0.42	0.61					0.94		0.44
 CHEMBL312750 Ki:28.0µM	0.58	0.78	0.79	0.94			0.78		0.82			0.85	
 CHEMBL73930 Ki:16.3µM										0.88			
 CHEMBL476121 Ki:830nM							0.96						

tid: 17047
chembl id: [CHEMBL2949](#)
name: Cyclooxygenase-1:Ovis aries

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL2408966 IC50:21.7µM													0.58
 CHEMBL117 IC50:39.3µM	0.71	1.00	0.76	0.82		0.55	0.79				0.94	0.77	0.54
 CHEMBL311498 IC50:9.10µM										0.87	1.00		
 CHEMBL365211 IC50:29.0µM								0.92					

tid: 104008
chembl id: [CHEMBL1741212](#)
name: Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase-6-phosphogluconolactonase:Plasmodium berghei

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1558563 IC50:8.25µM					0.48								
 CHEMBL463563 IC50:19.0µM	0.52	0.78	0.77				0.57	0.80			0.88		0.39
 CHEMBL1564355 IC50:26.6µM				0.93				0.97	0.84			0.89	
 CHEMBL1448387 IC50:17.6µM										0.96			

tid: 10752
chembl id: [CHEMBL1991](#)
name: Inhibitor of nuclear factor kappa B kinase beta sub-unit:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL75267 IC50:9.82µM	1.00	0.71	0.81	0.54	0.55	0.78	0.99	0.96			0.88	0.90	0.43
 CHEMBL4105195 IC50:6.23µM										0.96			
 CHEMBL6246 IC50:1.98µM	0.57												

tid: 100413
chembl id: [CHEMBL4898](#)
name: Neurotrophic tyrosine kinase receptor type 2:Homo sapi-ens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL75267 Kd:320nM	0.57	1.00	0.71		0.54	0.55	0.78	0.99	0.96	0.95	0.88	0.90	0.43
 CHEMBL1972355 Ki:3.16µM													0.82

tid: 11112
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4321](#)
 name: Cyclooxygenase-2:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL16171 IC50:1.07µM</p>													
<p>CHEMBL461230 IC50:10.00µM</p>													

0.73 0.89 0.46 0.51 0.74 0.96 0.87 0.91 0.88 0.89

0.52 0.88

0.57

tid: 104178
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1795096](#)
 name: mRNA interferase MazF:Escherichia coli K-12

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL457679 EC50:14.0µM	0.69	0.74	0.80	0.92	0.61	0.76	0.74	0.95		1.00	0.79		0.43
 CHEMBL1601846 EC50:80.5µM									0.87		0.67		

tid: 100304
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4860](#)
 name: Apoptosis regulator Bcl-2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL3828618 Ki:4.60µM	0.54	0.82	0.71	0.86	0.60	0.48	0.70	0.93	0.93		0.94		0.38
 CHEMBL346119 Ki:691nM										1.00			
 CHEMBL259034 IC50:290nM												0.68	

tid: 108
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL225](#)
 name: Serotonin 2c (5-HT2c) receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:14.9µM	0.71		0.80		0.60			0.88	0.93		0.94		
 CHEMBL63354 Ki:2.56µM	1.00	0.66				0.62	0.69			0.86		0.86	0.60

tid: 101246
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL5586](#)
 name: Carbonyl reductase [NADPH] 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL117 IC50:670nM	0.71	1.00	0.76	0.82	0.55		0.79	0.90	0.86		0.94		0.54
 CHEMBL97453 IC50:3.78µM						0.57							
 CHEMBL131921 IC50:12.7µM										0.80		0.81	

tid: 69
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1808](#)
 name: Angiotensin-converting enzyme:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL448040 IC50:69.2µM	0.80	0.86	0.54	0.82	0.65	0.78	0.50	0.99	0.96		0.94		0.62
 CHEMBL477740 IC50:35.4µM										1.00		0.97	

tid: 11943
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3964](#)
 name: Phospholipase C-gamma-1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth	
 CHEMBL210208 IC50:14.2µM							0.54							
 CHEMBL63354 IC50:29.0µM	0.65	1.00	0.66				0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.86	0.60
 CHEMBL1563898 IC50:67.5µM							0.67							

tid: 11626
chembl id: [CHEMBL3116](#)
name: Cyclin-dependent kinase 9:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL243664 Ki:1.26μM</p>	0.60	0.78	0.77	0.86	0.52	0.55	0.78				0.88		0.33
<p>CHEMBL490355 IC50:2.16μM</p>								0.90	0.78	0.93		0.77	

tid: 17018
chembl id: [CHEMBL4078](#)
name: Acetylcholinesterase:Electrophorus electricus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL418068 IC50:637nM</p>					0.56								
<p>CHEMBL276915 IC50:85.0µM</p>	0.59	1.00					0.75				0.81	0.77	
<p>CHEMBL3577529 IC50:22.5µM</p>			0.70	0.82									
<p>CHEMBL465185 IC50:5.20µM</p>						0.61							
<p>CHEMBL2165237 IC50:20.0µM</p>								0.93		0.96			
<p>CHEMBL252642 IC50:9.10µM</p>									0.83				

structure

mfp1

featmfp1

rdkit7

pattern

ap_bits

tt_bits

fp2

pubchem

cdk_maccs

graph

substructure

hybridization

klekota_roth

[CHEMBL2337265](#)

IC50:190nM

0.60

tid: 118219

chembl id: [CHEMBL4295974](#)

name: Regulator of G-protein signaling 17:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1438439 IC50:18.3µM	0.67	0.87	0.62	0.88	0.67	0.52	0.55	0.92	1.00	0.89	1.00	0.86	0.53

tid: 10198
chembl id: [CHEMBL4306](#)
name: Voltage-gated potassium channel subunit Kv1.5:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL243664 IC50:3.30µM	0.60	0.78	0.77	0.86	0.52	0.55	0.78		0.77		0.88	0.77	0.33
 CHEMBL203909 EC50:5.00µM								0.88		0.84			

tid: 272
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1869](#)
 name: Ornithine decarboxylase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:26.0µM	0.71	0.87			0.60	0.49			0.93		0.94		0.47
 CHEMBL375582 IC50:3.40µM			0.68	0.92			0.68	0.89				0.81	
 CHEMBL451703 IC50:2.10µM										0.87			

tid: 101300
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL5719](#)
 name: Cell division protein kinase 8:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1972346 Ki:251nM					0.53								0.43
 CHEMBL243664 Ki:631nM	0.60	0.78	0.77	0.86		0.55	0.78	0.88	0.77	0.77	0.88	0.77	

tid: 105083
chembl id: [CHEMBL2111389](#)
name: CDK9/cyclin T1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL16171 IC50:193nM	0.48	0.78	0.73	0.89	0.46	0.51	0.74	0.96	0.87	0.91	0.88	0.89	0.32

tid: 107899
chembl id: [CHEMBL3038473](#)
name: CDK7/Cyclin H/MNAT1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL16171 IC50:12.3µM	0.48	0.78	0.73	0.89	0.46	0.51	0.74	0.96	0.87	0.91	0.88	0.89	0.32

tid: 107895
chembl id: [CHEMBL3038469](#)
name: CDK2/Cyclin A:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL16171 IC50:1.46µM	0.48	0.78	0.73	0.89	0.46	0.51	0.74	0.96	0.87	0.91	0.88	0.89	0.32

tid: 105509
chembl id: [CHEMBL2221347](#)
name: Voltage-gated potassium channel, IKs; KCNQ1(Kv7.1)/KCNE1(MinK):Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL243664 IC50:81.4µM</p>	0.60	0.78	0.77	0.86	0.52	0.55	0.78	0.88	0.77	0.77	0.88	0.77	0.33

tid: 11153
chembl id: [CHEMBL1964](#)
name: Voltage-gated potassium channel subunit Kv4.3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL243664 IC50:9.30µM</p>	0.60	0.78	0.77	0.86	0.52	0.55	0.78	0.88	0.77	0.77	0.88	0.77	0.33

tid: 133
chembl id: [CHEMBL235](#)
name: Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor
gamma:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL469824 EC50:3.10µM					0.45				0.81			0.85	0.36
 CHEMBL476121 IC50:5.40µM	0.54		0.72	0.92		0.45	0.74						
 CHEMBL226512 IC50:2.50µM			0.78					0.96			0.88		
 CHEMBL127671 EC50:23.1µM										0.93			

tid: 13000
chembl id: [CHEMBL332](#)
name: Matrix metalloproteinase-1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL187265 IC50:11.4µM	0.74	0.86	0.53	0.82	0.65	0.67	0.48	0.95	0.96	0.89	0.94	0.86	0.62

tid: 187
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1783](#)
 name: Vascular endothelial growth factor A:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL63354 Kd:16.5nM	0.65	1.00	0.66	0.62	0.41	0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87		0.94	0.86	0.60
 CHEMBL2335722 Kd:16.0nM										1.00			

tid: 103950

chembl id: [CHEMBL1697671](#)

name: Placenta growth factor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL63354 Kd:8.20nM	0.65	1.00	0.66	0.62	0.41	0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87		0.94	0.86	0.60
 CHEMBL2335722 Kd:11.0nM										1.00			

tid: 101158
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL5346](#)
 name: Tyrosinase:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL13486 IC50:5.23µM	0.64	0.87			0.61	0.49			0.96		0.88		0.71
 CHEMBL242739 IC50:11.2µM			0.56	0.80			0.54	0.96				0.90	
 CHEMBL2016934 IC50:9.00µM										0.98			

tid: 114

chembl id: [CHEMBL226](#)

name: Adenosine A1 receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL3939546 Ki:6.28μM					0.72	0.63		0.94					
 CHEMBL283196 IC50:1.13μM							0.63						
 CHEMBL44 IC50:19.9μM		0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80					0.80	0.94	0.81	
 CHEMBL2397719 Ki:14.7μM								0.93					
 CHEMBL7334 Ki:501nM													0.57

tid: 17106
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL4105](#)
 name: Serotonin 1d (5-HT1d) receptor:Sus scrofa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL63354 Ki:4.09µM	0.65	1.00	0.66		0.41	0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.86	0.60
 CHEMBL27403 IC50:123nM				0.65									

tid: 101017
chembl id: [CHEMBL5566](#)
name: 1-phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-1:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL63354 IC50:29.0µM	0.65	1.00	0.66	0.62	0.41	0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.86	0.60

tid: 17102
chembl id: [CHEMBL4103](#)
name: Delta opioid receptor:Sus scrofa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL63354 Ki:36.5nM	0.65	1.00	0.66	0.62	0.41	0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.86	0.60

tid: 100933
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL5366](#)
 name: Poly [ADP-ribose] polymerase 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth	
 CHEMBL1836301 IC50:4.80µM							0.81	0.43						
 CHEMBL63354 IC50:10.3µM	0.65	1.00	0.66				0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.86	0.60

tid: 130

chembl id: [CHEMBL234](#)

name: Dopamine D3 receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL63354 Ki:1.24µM	0.65	1.00	0.66		0.41	0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.86	0.60
 CHEMBL3780975 Ki:1.37µM					0.72								

tid: 103079
chembl id: [CHEMBL1075145](#)
name: Transitional endoplasmic reticulum ATPase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL63354 IC50:8.98µM	0.65	1.00	0.66		0.41	0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.86	0.60
 CHEMBL496 IC50:5.49µM					0.71								

tid: 104757
chembl id: [CHEMBL2095172](#)
name: GABA-A receptor; alpha-1/beta-2/gamma-2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL63354 EC50:3.60µM	0.65	1.00	0.66		0.41	0.62	0.69	0.85	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.86	0.60
 CHEMBL510120 EC50:25.0µM					0.74								

tid: 104436
chembl id: [CHEMBL1938225](#)
name: dTDP-4-dehydrorhamnose reductase:Myco bacterium tuberculosis

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL375328 IC50:900nM	0.54	1.00			0.59	0.53		0.91	0.96		0.88	0.88	
 CHEMBL175266 IC50:15.0µM			0.59	0.75			0.71			0.89			0.27

tid: 10200

chembl id: [CHEMBL2085](#)

name: Macrophage migration inhibitory factor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL13486 IC50:38.0nM	0.64	0.87	0.55	0.78	0.61		0.53	0.93	0.96	0.82	0.88	0.82	0.71
 CHEMBL6246 IC50:4.77µM							0.54						

tid: 107653

chembl id: [CHEMBL2424504](#)

name: Lysine-specific demethylase 5A:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL3792463 IC50:25.0µM	0.62	0.86			0.52	0.51		0.97	0.82	0.95	0.88	0.90	
 CHEMBL3794377 IC50:4.20µM			0.68	0.81			0.62						
 CHEMBL1084265 IC50:15.0µM													0.30

tid: 3
chembl id: [CHEMBL1827](#)
name: Phosphodiesterase 5A:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL193059 IC50:700nM</p>	0.59	0.75	0.60	0.69	0.75	0.97	0.76	1.00	0.84	0.46			
<p>CHEMBL283196 IC50:2.30µM</p>	0.79									0.65			
<p>CHEMBL371562 IC50:1.29µM</p>			0.88										

tid: 104509
chembl id: [CHEMBL2016431](#)
name: NEDD8-activating enzyme E1 regulatory subunit:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL2322196 IC50:10.00µM</p>	0.76	1.00	0.74	0.63	0.39	0.48	0.81	0.84	0.87	0.82	0.94	0.82	0.40

tid: 101277
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL5658](#)
 name: Prostaglandin E synthase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL71115 IC50:7.10µM	0.64	0.80			0.62						0.83		
 CHEMBL3923896 IC50:11.3µM						0.57	0.67					0.75	
 CHEMBL4098732 IC50:1.80µM			0.69	0.84				0.95					
 CHEMBL1984096 IC50:1.10µM										1.00			
 CHEMBL297453 IC50:1.80µM										0.88			

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
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CHEMBL2147420

IC50:7.40μM

0.27

tid: 11872
chembl id: [CHEMBL2758](#)
name: Mannose-6-phosphate isomerase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1597177 IC50:30.0µM					0.55								
 CHEMBL175266 IC50:3.55µM		0.82					0.71				0.76	0.72	
 CHEMBL1566632 IC50:44.8µM					0.89								
 CHEMBL522983 IC50:31.0µM		0.59	0.68						0.88				
 CHEMBL33027 IC50:21.3µM						0.54							

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL1479103 IC50:26.4μM</p>										0.96			
<p>CHEMBL560919 IC50:29.6μM</p>							0.92						
<p>CHEMBL1536196 IC50:25.9μM</p>												0.31	

tid: 248
chembl id: [CHEMBL1835](#)
name: Thromboxane-A synthase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:7.72µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49		0.88	0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL283196 IC50:6.76µM							0.63						
 CHEMBL267475 IC50:10.00µM										0.89			

tid: 12832
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3072](#)
 name: Androgen Receptor:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:85.1µM	0.71	0.87		0.80	0.60	0.49		0.88	0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL275638 IC50:77.6µM			0.59				0.63						
 CHEMBL195033 IC50:18.6µM										0.82			

tid: 11755
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1841](#)
 name: Tyrosine-protein kinase FYN:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:58.2µM	0.71	0.87	0.58		0.60	0.49		0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL26260 IC50:2.51µM							0.63						
 CHEMBL1972355 Ki:2.00µM			0.82										

tid: 103719
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1293286](#)
 name: Polyadenylate-binding protein 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL66953 IC50:47.9µM	0.60				0.46	0.52			0.76				
 CHEMBL485247 IC50:33.7µM		0.78	0.73	0.90			0.77	0.95			0.76	0.86	0.38
 CHEMBL1350188 IC50:91.1µM										0.93			

tid: 103925
chembl id: [CHEMBL1687677](#)
name: Pancreatic triacylglycerol lipase:Sus scrofa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL3422849 IC50:63.0µM</p>	0.57	0.79			0.66	0.71	0.69	0.97		0.98		0.74	
<p>CHEMBL518543 IC50:18.6µM</p>			0.58	0.79							0.79		0.32
<p>CHEMBL3422848 IC50:56.4µM</p>									0.87				

tid: 100448
chembl id: [CHEMBL4506](#)
name: NAD-dependent deacetylase sirtuin 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL3698622 IC50:1.84µM</p>	0.60	0.79	0.61	0.81	0.68	0.53	0.70	0.93	0.87	0.89			0.38
<p>CHEMBL2314699 IC50:31.2µM</p>												0.76	
<p>CHEMBL2314710 IC50:2.80µM</p>											0.82		

tid: 11472
chembl id: [CHEMBL4026](#)
name: Signal transducer and activator of transcription 3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:24.8µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL4171066 EC50:834nM										1.00			

tid: 103947
chembl id: [CHEMBL1697668](#)
name: Solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 1B1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL44 IC50:9.12µM</p>	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51		0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
<p>CHEMBL4802105 IC50:9.00µM</p>										0.98			
<p>CHEMBL9509 IC50:6.17µM</p>								0.88					

tid: 104062
chembl id: [CHEMBL1743121](#)
name: Solute carrier organic anion transporter family member
1B3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL44 IC50:3.89µM</p>	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51		0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
<p>CHEMBL4802105 IC50:36.4µM</p>										0.98			
<p>CHEMBL9509 IC50:4.27µM</p>								0.88					

tid: 100911
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL5313](#)
 name: Heat shock factor protein 1:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL414890 EC50:4.28µM					0.86	0.55		0.92		0.95			
 CHEMBL1365850 EC50:19.2µM	0.60	0.68	0.60				0.47	0.79		0.88		0.28	
 CHEMBL1468522 EC50:15.0µM							0.49						
 CHEMBL1428823 EC50:65.4µM												0.71	

tid: 12643
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3305](#)
 name: Testis-specific androgen-binding protein:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 Kd:39.8μM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49		0.88	0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL265940 Kd:832nM							0.61						
 CHEMBL194392 IC50:22.4μM										0.89			

tid: 103524
chembl id: [CHEMBL1250410](#)
name: Solute carrier family 2, facilitated glucose transporter member 4:Mus musculus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:20.0µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51		0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL431701 Ki:60.0µM								0.88		0.86			

tid: 12453
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3358](#)
 name: Monoamine oxidase A:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:40.0µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51		0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL434510 IC50:23.4µM								0.91		0.81			

tid: 17019
chembl id: [CHEMBL2860](#)
name: Cyclooxygenase-1:Bos taurus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL311498 IC50:80.0µM</p>					0.47				0.87	1.00			
<p>CHEMBL504481 IC50:97.0µM</p>	0.52	0.68	0.60	0.89		0.38	0.50	0.92			0.88	0.83	0.36

tid: 11359
chembl id: [CHEMBL288](#)
name: Phosphodiesterase 4D:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL512578 IC50:2.91µM		0.79			0.56							0.65	
 CHEMBL4174381 IC50:1.88µM			0.67				0.69		0.74				
 CHEMBL371562 IC50:630nM				0.88							0.79		
 CHEMBL485777 IC50:260nM		0.63				0.55							0.33
 CHEMBL323197 IC50:1.31µM							0.91			0.89			

tid: 321
chembl id: [CHEMBL1993](#)
name: DNA (cytosine-5)-methyltransferase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:30.0µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93		0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL1322547 IC50:5.25µM										0.81			

tid: 30016
chembl id: [CHEMBL3834](#)
name: Tyrosine-protein kinase BMX:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:68.0µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47

tid: 8
chembl id: [CHEMBL1862](#)
name: Tyrosine-protein kinase ABL:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:10.00µM	0.71	0.87			0.60	0.49		0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47
 CHEMBL2408505 IC50:2.68µM							0.55						
 CHEMBL1972355 Ki:794nM					0.82								
 CHEMBL2408506 IC50:3.46µM			0.67										

tid: 11047
chembl id: [CHEMBL2897](#)
name: Dual specificity mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase
4:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:400nM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47

tid: 107
chembl id: [CHEMBL224](#)
name: Serotonin 2a (5-HT2a) receptor:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:10.5µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47

tid: 109557
chembl id: [CHEMBL3392945](#)
name: Alpha-mannosidase:Canavalia ensiformis

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:49.0µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47

tid: 12450
chembl id: [CHEMBL3992](#)
name: Cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator:Rattus norvegicus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 Kd:40.0μM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47

tid: 155
chembl id: [CHEMBL238](#)
name: Dopamine transporter:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:16.9µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47

tid: 11254
chembl id: [CHEMBL3751](#)
name: Estrogen-related receptor beta:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:395nM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47

tid: 106600
chembl id: [CHEMBL2366456](#)
name: Voltage-dependent L-type calcium channel subunit
alpha-1C:Cavia porcellus

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL44 IC50:20.0µM	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47

tid: 12056
chembl id: [CHEMBL3257](#)
name: Aldehyde oxidase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
	0.71	0.87	0.58	0.80	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.94	0.81	0.47
CHEMBL44 IC50:340nM													

tid: 110226
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL3708265](#)
 name: 7,8-dihydro-8-oxoguanine triphosphatase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL477921 IC50:57.0µM	0.60	0.86			0.62		0.47	0.99	0.93			0.90	0.46
 CHEMBL506229 IC50:1.70µM			0.49	0.84		0.58							
 CHEMBL488606 IC50:20.0µM										0.95			
 CHEMBL260553 IC50:2.00µM												0.84	

tid: 30
chembl id: [CHEMBL1935](#)
name: Aldehyde dehydrogenase:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL8145 IC50:9.00µM	0.59	0.87			0.54				0.89			0.81	0.38
 CHEMBL110038 IC50:3.50µM			0.66				0.63						
 CHEMBL491174 Ki:450nM				0.81		0.43					0.88		
 CHEMBL113113 IC50:70.0nM								0.88		0.89			

tid: 10131
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL2334](#)
 name: Caspase-3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1711590 IC50:19.0µM					0.53								
 CHEMBL484663 IC50:16.8µM	0.62	1.00	0.66	0.76			0.73	0.89	0.82		0.81	0.76	0.36
 CHEMBL1569645 IC50:11.0µM													0.45
 CHEMBL1605599 IC50:25.7µM											1.00		

tid: 104003
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1741207](#)
 name: Sentrin-specific protease 8:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1711590 IC50:5.94μM							0.53						
 CHEMBL484663 IC50:11.6μM	0.62	1.00	0.66	0.76			0.73	0.89	0.82		0.81	0.76	0.36
 CHEMBL1569645 IC50:69.1μM							0.45						
 CHEMBL1605599 IC50:17.4μM										1.00			

tid: 104011
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1741215](#)
 name: Sentrin-specific protease 6:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1711590 IC50:6.00µM					0.53								
 CHEMBL484663 IC50:87.7µM	0.62	1.00	0.66	0.76			0.73	0.89	0.82		0.81	0.76	0.36
 CHEMBL1569645 IC50:15.1µM													0.45
 CHEMBL1605599 IC50:4.61µM													1.00

tid: 104009
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1741213](#)
 name: Sentrin-specific protease 7:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1711590 IC50:4.49µM					0.53								
 CHEMBL484663 IC50:9.80µM	0.62	1.00	0.66	0.76			0.73	0.89	0.82		0.81	0.76	0.36
 CHEMBL1569645 IC50:9.80µM													0.45
 CHEMBL1605599 IC50:12.7µM													1.00

tid: 19636
chembl id: [CHEMBL3463](#)
name: Human immunodeficiency virus type 2 integrase:Human immunodeficiency virus 2

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL366356 IC50:2.50µM					0.54								
 CHEMBL175266 IC50:1.86µM	0.82	0.59	0.75		0.47	0.71	0.89	0.86	0.89		0.72	0.27	
 CHEMBL293914 IC50:1.00µM	0.44										0.88		

tid: 117032
chembl id: [CHEMBL3883319](#)
name: Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(I)/G(S)/G(T) subunit beta-1/gamma-2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL3728757 IC50:200nM			0.57		0.62	0.53		0.89					0.16
 CHEMBL1723511 IC50:130nM		0.70					0.63	0.90			0.74		
 CHEMBL502775 IC50:200nM				0.78								0.90	
 CHEMBL3727794 IC50:700nM			0.45							0.91			

tid: 103677
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1293244](#)
 name: Beta-lactamase:Pseudomonas aeruginosa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1392848 IC50:8.62μM					0.54	0.57							
 CHEMBL1571034 IC50:5.62μM			0.57				0.63	0.89	0.82	0.85	0.82	0.87	
 CHEMBL1605743 IC50:399nM	0.54	1.00											0.29
 CHEMBL1547938 IC50:14.1μM					0.72								

tid: 103693
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1293260](#)
 name: Beta-lactamase:Salmonella choleraesuis (strain SC-B67)

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1392848 IC50:3.41µM							0.54 0.57						
 CHEMBL1571034 IC50:2.13µM			0.57				0.63 0.89 0.82 0.85 0.82 0.87						
 CHEMBL1605743 IC50:190nM							0.54 1.00						0.29
 CHEMBL1547938 IC50:7.50µM						0.72							

tid: 103679
 · chembl id: [CHEMBL1293246](#)
 name: Beta Lactamase:Pseudomonas aeruginosa

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL1392848 IC50:4.47µM							0.54 0.57						
 CHEMBL1571034 IC50:5.11µM			0.57				0.63 0.89 0.82 0.85 0.82 0.87						
 CHEMBL1605743 IC50:374nM							0.54 1.00						0.29
 CHEMBL1705527 IC50:3.60µM						0.80							

tid: 11757
chembl id: [CHEMBL2284](#)
name: Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase liver:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL502775 IC50:15.8µM													
			0.57	0.78	0.59	0.51	0.56	0.89	0.81			0.90	
 CHEMBL71271 IC50:38.9µM													
			0.59	0.80								0.67	
 CHEMBL3604098 IC50:1.41µM													
											0.96		
 CHEMBL69085 IC50:30.9µM													
													0.20

tid: 119121
chembl id: [CHEMBL4523371](#)
name: Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase
10:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL6338 IC50:330nM	0.57	0.73	0.40	0.76	0.60	0.69	0.43	0.93	0.90	0.83	0.67	0.77	0.25

tid: 115316
chembl id: [CHEMBL3713355](#)
name: Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 2:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL6338 IC50:1.48µM</p>	0.57	0.73			0.76	0.60	0.69	0.43	0.93	0.90	0.83	0.67	0.77
<p>CHEMBL6246 IC50:1.22µM</p>					0.41								0.27

tid: 119150
chembl id: [CHEMBL4523400](#)
name: Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 6:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL6338 IC50:1.83µM	0.57	0.73	0.40	0.76	0.60	0.69	0.43	0.93	0.90	0.83	0.67	0.77	0.25

tid: 119032
chembl id: [CHEMBL4523282](#)
name: Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 1:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL6338 IC50:2.46µM	0.57	0.73	0.40	0.76	0.60	0.69	0.43	0.93	0.90	0.83	0.67	0.77	0.25

tid: 119041
chembl id: [CHEMBL4523291](#)
name: Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 3:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL6338 IC50:1.61μM	0.57	0.73	0.40	0.76	0.60	0.69	0.43	0.93	0.90	0.83	0.67	0.77	0.25

tid: 119177
chembl id: [CHEMBL4523427](#)
name: Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase
14:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
<p>CHEMBL6338 IC50:460nM</p>	0.57	0.73	0.40	0.76	0.60	0.69	0.43	0.93	0.90	0.83	0.67	0.77	0.25

tid: 119142
chembl id: [CHEMBL4523392](#)
name: Polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase
13:Homo sapiens

similarity analysis

structure	mfp1	featmfp1	rdkit7	pattern	ap_bits	tt_bits	fp2	pubchem	cdk_maccs	graph	substructure	hybridization	klekota_roth
 CHEMBL6338 IC50:13.8μM	0.57	0.73	0.40	0.76	0.60	0.69	0.43	0.93	0.90	0.83	0.67	0.77	0.25